

CHARACTERISATION OF A HEATER BLANKET FOR *IN SITU* COMPOSITE PATCH REPAIRS

R. M. J. Kemp
Materials and Structures Department
Defence Research Agency
Farnborough, Hampshire
England, GU14 6TD

ABSTRACT

Temperature profiles under a resistive heater blanket have been measured using thermocouples and infrared thermography. The blanket dimensions, substrate size, control thermocouple position and incorporation of a heat diffuser have been investigated and the implications for repair practice discussed.

Keywords: Repair, patching, composites, temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

Damage sustained by composite structures is routinely repaired *in situ* using hot-bonded composite repair patches. Since the parent laminates are manufactured under high pressure (typically 690 kPa) and at high temperature (*eg* 120 or 180°C) the patch repair operation is ideally cured using an autoclave. For many components however, the monocoque composite structure is larger than the autoclave capacity and cannot be easily disassembled, hence the repair must be performed *in situ*. Commercial equipment is used for this purpose – termed a ‘hot-bond-controller’ (HBC) – which provides a vacuum source and controlled, programmed heat input typically via a resistance heater blanket.

Uniform heating of an *in situ* composite patch repair is often difficult to achieve since the heat sink effects of the substrate varies with substrate thickness and presence of substructure. The most commonly used heating methods are resistance heating via a heater blanket [1] and radiant heater lamps [2]. The former has the disadvantage of being a localised heat source producing thermal gradients, but has the advantages of being easy to use, small in size, lightweight and able to heat most curved surfaces. Heat lamps heat a larger area of substrate which helps to reduce thermal gradients although the indirect nature of heat input can produce uneven heating [3].

The simplicity of use of resistance heater blankets and their small size makes them the best choice for field repairs and they are widely used for general maintenance applications. Although general instructions for the use of heater blankets have been developed (*eg* [1,4]) little quantitative data relevant to their use is available. The present work aimed to quantify their limitations in order to improve best practice. In particular, the positioning of the control thermocouple; the size of heater blanket, and the use of a heat diffuser have been assessed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

2.1 Materials and equipment

A commercial HBC was used to control the blanket temperature and provide a nominal 1 atmosphere (100 kPa) vacuum. Type 'J' thermocouples were used to monitor the temperature (-ve:Fe; +ve:40%Ni, 60%Cu) one of which (PV) was used as the controlling thermocouple. The majority of the tests investigated a heater blanket of dimensions 150 x 300 mm which comprised of a resistive heating element (Figure 1a) rated at 360 W encapsulated in a silicone rubber mat. A smaller mat 150 x 150 mm (Figure 1b) was used for some tests (180 W power rating). The nominal power output of both mats was 0.8 W/cm^2 and for the majority of measurements the heater blanket was in contact with the substrate.

For thermocouple measurements the 'substrate' was a 16-ply carbon fibre/914 laminate of dimensions 300 x 155 mm (small); 540 x 300 mm (large). An 8-ply (0, 90) repair patch of T800-924 was cured for through-thickness temperature monitoring. The thermocouples were situated through the thickness at the corners of the patch to minimise the heat sink effects of the wire. The control thermocouples were situated at the bond line.

2.2 Temperature measurement

Temperature profiles were measured using Type K thermocouples comprising of chromium-nickel + aluminium-nickel {-ve:95%Ni + 5%(Al, Si, Mn); +ve:90%Ni + 10%Cr}. These were connected to a (compensated) 12-bank rotary switch, and the output was monitored using a digital thermometer (DVM). Temperatures were monitored manually. The temperature monitored by the HBC was within $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ of the independent DVM reading.

Fig 1 X-radiographs of a) large and b) small heater blankets

2.3 Thermal imaging

For the thermal imaging tests a 23-ply (0, 90) carbon fibre laminate (1000 x 1000 mm) was clamped vertically to face the imaging camera. The surface to be imaged was painted matt black to increase emissivity.

The effect of a copper sheet heat diffuser (300 x 155 x 0.61 mm) was investigated by thermography, the diffuser being interposed between the heater blanket and substrate.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Effect of blanket size

The effect of heater blanket size on the thermal profiles measured between blanket and substrate are shown in Figure 2. The temperature was higher in the centre of the blanket in all cases. For the small square blanket the profiles were similar in the x and y directions and were similar to the x-axis profile of the oblong blanket. The temperature profile in the y-axis of the large oblong blanket showed a much less pronounced temperature gradient.

3.2 Effect of substrate size

The effect of substrate size on thermal profiles under the large heater mat are plotted in Figure 3. The thermal gradients were increased by the larger substrate, the effect being more pronounced across the width of the mat, indicating that both the substrate geometry and the blanket geometry influenced the thermal gradient.

3.3 Effect of control thermocouple position

Thermography-generated temperature profiles from the reverse side of the substrate for the control thermocouple at the centre (PV1) and edge (PV2) of the blanket are shown in Figure 4a&b. Controlling the edge of the blanket to 120°C caused the temperature to be considerably higher in the centre of the blanket (*ie* 126°C) than when the centre was controlled at 120°C (109°C recorded). The temperature gradient near edge of the blanket was also influenced, being greater for PV2.

3.4 Effect of a heat diffuser

The effect of a copper sheet heat diffuser on the temperature distribution under the blanket is shown by the profiles in Figure 5a&b and the thermogram in Figure 5c. The diffuser reduced the peak temperature slightly compared to the blanket only, but had a beneficial effect on the heat distribution producing a 'flat-topped' temperature profile.

3.5 Thermal gradient through a patch

The temperature through the thickness of an 8-ply patch was monitored by embedded thermocouples. In order to minimise heat sink effects due to the thermocouple wires the 4 thermocouples were positioned at the corners of the patch. The temperature gradients for different PV positions (controlling at 180°C) are shown in Figure 6. The temperature gradient in the top 6 plies (nearest the heater mat) was approximately -0.7°C/ply. The gradient reversed near the substrate surface. For this small patch under the large heater blanket altering the control thermocouple position had minimal effect.

4 DISCUSSION

The aspect ratio (length:width) of the heater blanket was found to have a significant effect on the temperature profile (Figure 2). The long (y) axis of the blanket showed a less pronounced temperature gradient (av 0.07°C/mm) compared to the short (x) axis (av 0.33°C/mm). This was not due to the wiring arrangement since the small patch showed the same gradient normal to and parallel to the wiring direction. The effect was therefore a size effect related to the power density. Increasing the substrate size produced a large increase in the temperature gradient across the width of the blanket (Figure 3) and a small increase along the length. This indicated the major effect due to the thermal capacity (*ie* heat

Fig 2 Effects of heater blanket size on thermal gradients (S; small; L; large)

Fig 3 Effect of substrate size on temperature gradients

Fig 4 Effect of control thermocouple (PV) position
 a) B1-B2 axis b) A1-A2 axis c) thermogram for PV2

Fig 5

Fig 5 Effect of heat diffuser using PVI a) B1-B2 axis
b) A1-A2 axis c) thermogram with diffuser

sink effect) of the substrate. A larger heat sink increased the gradient and hence then reduced the area of substrate correctly heated. The results indicate that the use of a large heater blanket can avoid these problems, and under the present test conditions the correct temperatures could be achieved by using a heater blanket twice the dimensions of the repair patch (for PV at the edge of the repair).

The choice of control thermocouple (PV) position poses a serious problem for *in situ* repair. The measurements shown in Figure 4 indicate a 13°C change in peak temperature caused by altering the PV position. In practice, the repair is often monitored by a number of thermocouples, and during heat-up the thermocouple reading the lowest temperature is used as the control in an attempt to ensure that all of the repair is above the required temperature. The disadvantage of such an approach is that some areas of the repair may go well above the required cure temperature. A compromise would be to choose a combination of control temperature and PV position to give a temperature range within the manufacturers recommended curing range.

Interposing a metal heat diffuser between blanket and substrate had a marked improvement in the temperature gradient. The disadvantages are the need to shape the diffuser to follow the surface/patch contours and the possibility that a poor fit will produce regions of low temperature.

The through-thickness profiles shown by Figure 6 were consistent for the 2 control thermocouple positions. Near the surface of the patch a temperature drop of 0.25°C per ply was measured, which is lower than the range of 0.6 to 1°C per ply measured elsewhere [3]. The disparity may be due to the position of the thermocouples at the patch corners. The results highlight the need to account for the temperature drop through the patch if the control thermocouple is on the top surface (eg 5°C drop for a 16-ply patch). The slope change near the substrate surface is explained by enhanced heat input at the corners of the patch. The temperature gradient partly explains the apparently low temperature values measured by thermography. The use in practice of a tapered patch edge (ply drop-off) will lessen the extent of through-thickness temperature gradient.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The temperature profile under a heater blanket is influenced by blanket size, heat capacity of the substrate and control thermocouple position. A considerable temperature gradient also exists through the thickness of the patch and all these factors must be considered during the design and curing of a patch. The results indicated that the heater blanket should be of the order of twice the size of the repair patch.

Fig 6 Temperature gradient through 8 - ply patch

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by DDOR/3/5/7/8/(MOD); DAir Eng(RAF);DTi Air Division; DSpt Pol(RAF) whose support is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. Middleton D.H. '*Composite Materials in Aircraft Structures*' Longman Scientific & Technical, Harlow, 1990
2. Armstrong K.B in Proc Conf '*Bonding and Repair of Composites*' Metropole Hotel, NEC Birmingham, July 1989, pp 93-99
3. Marsh R.E. '*An investigation of the infrared curing of carbon-epoxy repair patches*' MEng Report, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Leeds, April 1992
4. Myhre S.H. '*Advanced Composite Repair Guide*' Northrop Corporation Aircraft Division (USAF Wright Aeronautical Laboratories Contract No. F33615-79-C-3217), 1982

© British Crown Copyright 1993/DRA Published with the permission of the Controller of Her Britannic Majesties Stationery Office

ADVANCED FABRICS

